

Comparing repository systems

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Repositories

For this assignment Ckan in the version 2.8 and the Fedora backend version Fedora commons 4.7.5 was selected.

Github

The migration tool (RepoMigrate) can be found under the following link:

<https://Github.com/alexschwarzresearch/repo-migrate>

RepoMigrate Usage

The tool is a command line program which has three possible commands. The output of the help command can be seen in fig. 1.


```
alex@ubuntu: ~/Documents/RepoMigrate
(venv) alex@ubuntu:~/Documents/RepoMigrate$ python repo_migrate.py -h
usage: repo_migrate.py [-h] (-l {ckan,fedora} | -m)

List the contents of either repository or migrate the data from ckan to
fedora.

optional arguments:
  -h, --help            show this help message and exit
  -l {ckan,fedora}, --list {ckan,fedora}
  -m, --migrate
```

Fig. 1: Help output

The second command (--list) requires the repository which will be listed. Fig. 2 displays the output for the Ckan repository with the demo content.


```
alex@ubuntu: ~/Documents/RepoMigrate
(venv) alex@ubuntu:~/Documents/RepoMigrate$ python repo_migrate.py -l ckan
+-----+
|Various Content|
+-----+
author: Alexander S.
description: The data consists of various text, data, image, audio, video as well as source code files.
license_id: cc-by
file(s) [12]:
- architectural-design-architecture-buildings-692103.jpg
- aumasson_2013_blake2b.pdf
- Darude - Sandstorm.mp3
- bertonni_2011_keccakref.pdf
- beach-bird-s-eye-view-daylight-1038374.jpg
- oceans-eight-trailer-2_h480p.mov
- the-predator-trailer-1_h480p.mov
- Hardwell - Eclipse.mp3
- dmp_creator.py
- dmp_lanner.py
- gdp_csv.csv
- Meteorite-Landings.csv
```

Fig. 2: Demo output of RepoMigrate list command

The tool displays the most relevant information of each collection in the repository together with a list of included files. During the design phase of the program a more in depth representation was considered but was ultimately discarded in favor of a clearer solution. For future consideration would be an optional verbose flag.

After the migration the Fedora output is identical to the Ckan output and is therefore not separately depicted in another screenshot.

Since the tool supports only one migration direction, no additional parameters for the migrate command are needed. If the tool finishes the migration, it displays a success message.

RepoMigrate Implementation

The tool is written in python 3 with the help of the requests¹ package and PyLD². Overall the implementation of the tool was quite straight-forward with no major problems. Nevertheless, there were some parts which turned out to be tricky.

An example is the population process of the Fedora repository during the migration step. Here the actual file and the metadata cannot be uploaded in one step due to the API restrictions. In the end the tool updates the metadata with a sparql request.

Also, the mapping of the metadata between the two repositories was not trivial. This was due to the fact that Fedora does, for the most part, not have a fixed metadata schema. Instead, linked data triples are used to describe the content of the repository. The phrase for the most part refers to a part of the metadata which is actually strictly repository managed and can therefore be considered a fixed schema. This includes the creation and modified time as well as the parent and child nodes. Therefore, all metadata fields of Ckan had to be translated to a linked data format.

Comparison

In this section Ckan and Fedora will be compared in several categories both in a general way and regarding specific experiences which appeared while using the repository systems.

Installation Ckan:

Ckan provides three installing options. These are an operating system package, from source code and with Docker Compose. For this comparison the operating system package was chosen. The overall process worked well but you had to install a few required technologies manually. The steps to install Ckan consisted of the installing of the Ckan package together with additionally required packages (nginx, apache2, etc.), the installing and configuring of PostgreSQL, as well as the installing and configuring of Solr. In order to upload files the optional FileStore had to be configured as well.

The Ckan supporting community³ is large and active. There are non-technical forums, technical mailing lists, Github issues and several other options to find or get answers to problems. During the experimentation phase after the installation certain files could not be updated and an error message mentioning the file size was displayed. A simple google search lead to a stackoverflow post which ultimately mentioned the right configuration option in order to resolve the problem. This example further strengthens the experience of the positive Ckan community.

¹ <http://docs.python-requests.org>

² <https://github.com/digitalbazaar/pyld>

³ <https://Ckan.org/community/>

The overall quality of the Ckan documentation⁴ is very good. Especially the installation process was detailed and complete. The documentation for the changing of metadata schema⁵ on the other hand was not perfect. The biggest problem turned out to be that the main concern of the section was the metadata schema of datasets. Only at the very end a paragraph explained that the resource metadata can be customized similarly. This part forgets to mention the creation of a template file without which the customization does not take effect on the site. The problem was found with the help of a Stackoverflow post which explained that the needed file is actually in the example code but is just not mentioned in the actual documentation.

Installation Fedora:

There are essentially three ways to install Fedora. The first one is a one-click run application and the second one is via a servlet container. The servlet container option is meant for production environments and offers a greater customization. Besides that there are also vagrant and docker images which build on an Ubuntu machine and work out of the box. For this project the one-click run application was chosen. In contrast to the Ckan installation which took quite some time it was a positive surprise that the one-click application is indeed as simple as it sounds. A jar file is executed which opens a popup where the port can be changed and Fedora started. After that, Fedora can be accessed at the chosen port.

The official Fedora supporting community⁶ mainly consists of mailing lists, a slack team as well as an IRC channel. It is not easy to estimate the size of the supporting community. Based on the Github repo activity it seems to be significantly smaller in comparison to Ckan but this could also not be as significant for the actual numbers as one would assume. A possible reason could be that Github is not used for issue tracking. Instead, there exists a Jira instance at the Duraspace website⁷.

The search for problems turned out to be harder than that for Ckan. The biggest challenge hereby was it to find Fedora commons specific solutions. In almost all cases everything but solutions concerning Fedora commons were found. This has to do with the connection to the repository systems which build on top of Fedora (e.g. Islandora). On the web this behavior is understandable but at the documentation page⁸ it is frustrating. The search function was basically unusable since no matter which topics where searched, each hit was either on a DSpace or an Islandora page.

The tight coupling of the documentation pages of different products was at least in my case very unhelpful. You always have to check if you are still in the section of your product or if you accidentally clicked on the wrong link and are suddenly in a different documentation. Regardless of this behavior also the quality of the documentation content was subjectively not as good as the Ckan documentation. This can be seen for example at the API section⁹. Besides the fact that in the accept header a semicolon-separated other profile header is concatenated, which in itself is another matter, the quotation marks do not match. Not only that, but they are also escaped which at least in my case lead to a bad request response code. Naturally these are very specific inconsistencies but in my experience this example was actually representative for the most part.

⁴ <http://docs.Ckan.org/en/2.8/contents.html>

⁵ <http://docs.Ckan.org/en/2.8/extensions/adding-custom-fields.html>

⁶ <https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/FF/Mailing+Lists+etc>

⁷ <https://jira.duraspace.org/projects/FCREPO/>

⁸ <https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/FEDORA475/Fedora+4.7.5+Documentation>

⁹ <https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/FEDORA475/RESTful+HTTP+API>

The documentation is also incomplete in several cases. The PUT option which lets you replace triples associated with a resource has a warning which explains that some resource properties are repository managed and cannot be modified. But there is no list of properties which actually have this restriction. So in the end the only option you are left with is a trial and error approach to find out which properties are repository managed.

Content Organization Ckan:

Ckan uses the default Python library `mimetypes`¹⁰ with the `strict` parameter set to `true`. Therefore, only official types¹¹ registered with IANA are detected automatically. If this is not the case “application/octet-stream” will be assigned. It is possible to register custom types with the `mimetypes` library.

Collections are supported and called datasets. Versioning is also supported although relatively hidden. It is possible to add “history” in the URL in order to display a revision history. Fig. 3 shows the revision history for the demo dataset.

Revision	Timestamp	Author	Log Message
264 ...	May 12, 2018, 16:27 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
db7 ...	May 12, 2018, 00:29 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
8d9 ...	May 12, 2018, 00:28 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
e98 ...	May 12, 2018, 00:27 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
0dd ...	May 12, 2018, 00:27 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
ecb ...	May 12, 2018, 00:26 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
3d3 ...	May 12, 2018, 00:25 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
04f ...	May 12, 2018, 00:24 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
34d ...	May 12, 2018, 00:15 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
d4b ...	May 12, 2018, 00:13 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
0e3 ...	May 12, 2018, 00:11 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
e61 ...	May 11, 2018, 20:20 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
34a ...	May 11, 2018, 20:20 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
140 ...	May 11, 2018, 20:13 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
88c ...	May 11, 2018, 20:08 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
4d7 ...	May 11, 2018, 20:08 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content
841 ...	May 11, 2018, 20:05 (CEST)	alex	REST API: Update object various-content

Fig. 3: Revision history of demo content

Ckan uses UUIDs version 4 as identifiers.

Content Organization Fedora:

The content type support in fedora behaves similar to Ckan. All file types are supported and types which are not automatically detected receive the “application/octet-stream” value. This value can be changed to a different value. There does not seem to be a straight-forward way to add a new file type without changing the source code itself. But since fedora is a backend system the content type assignment can be done at a higher level.

¹⁰ <http://docs.python.org/2/library/mimetypes.html>

¹¹ <https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml>

Fedora uses linked data conventions to structure the repository. With that it is possible to create your own definitions for objects like collections. Fedora also has a version history with the difference that snapshots of a node have to be created manually. Fig. 4 shows the overview of manually created snapshots for the demo dataset.

Fig. 4: Version snapshots of demo content

Snapshots can be viewed, deleted or used to overwrite their active node.

Fedora uses URIs to identify resources. These URIs can either be specified manually or generated with the help of a PID Minter. The internal PID Minter generates URIs with UUID v4 values. It is also possible to specify an external PID Minter service or to customize the internal Minter.

Metadata Ckan:

Per default Ckan lets the user add a name, a description and a format to a resource. Additionally, it saves several timestamps, ids, the size of the resource, the license of the parent collection, the state and whether it was uploaded or added via a URL, all of which can be seen in fig. 5.

Additional Information	
Field	Value
Data last updated	May 11, 2018
Metadata last updated	May 11, 2018
Created	May 11, 2018
Format	image/jpeg
License	Creative Commons Attribution
created	2 days ago
format	JPEG
has views	True
id	a744df2f-9653-426c-97b5-e7d1569673c9
last modified	2 days ago
mimetype	image/jpeg
on same domain	True
package id	82d412f0-318d-4696-a14c-82497a645c49
revision id	c61edfe1-b00e-4071-95cf-aa3650370609
size	3.8 MiB
state	active
uri type	upload
Hide	

Fig. 5: Example metadata fields for a resource

For collections Ckan provides the possibility to change the title, the description, tags, license, organization, visibility, source, version, author, author email, maintainer, maintainer email as well as custom key and value fields.

In order to change the default metadata standard one can create a plugin which customizes the default definition. The plugin has to be registered in a configuration file to take effect. Fig. 6 shows the additional bitrate and length field in the resource form which were added as part of the assignment.

The screenshot shows a web form for adding a new resource. At the top, there are two buttons: 'New resource' and 'All resources'. Below this, the 'Data:' section contains 'Upload' and 'Link' buttons. The 'bitrate:' field is a text input containing the word 'bitrate'. The 'length:' field is a text input containing the word 'length'. The 'Name:' field contains the text 'eg. January 2011 Gold Prices'. The 'Description:' field is a large text area with the placeholder text 'Some useful notes about the data' and a link 'You can use Markdown formatting here'. The 'Format:' field is a dropdown menu with the selected option 'eg. CSV, XML or JSON'. At the bottom right, there is a blue 'Add' button. A small note at the bottom left of the form states: 'This will be guessed automatically. Leave blank if you wish'.

Fig. 6: Additional metadata fields in the resource form

Metadata Fedora:

As mentioned during the migration tool description, metadata in Fedora is defined as linked data values. Per default this includes parent and child nodes, timestamps, creator, as well as types. Binary resources additionally receive a filename and mimetype metadata field, as well as a size and a generated hash.

Due to the linked data metadata approach of Fedora, it is not possible and also not needed to define a new standard. Desired metadata fields can just be added to the resources without additional preparation.

Content presentation Ckan:

Contents inside a dataset are presented as list with several individual icons, as displayed in fig. 7.

Various Content

The data consists of various text, data, image, audio, video as well as source code files.

Data and Resources

architectural-design-architecture-buildings-692 ... Picture of architecture.	Explore
aumasson_2013_blake2b.pdf Paper for blake2b	Explore
Darude - Sandstorm.mp3 Darude Sandstorm song	Explore
bertonl_2011_keccakref.pdf Keccak reference paper	Explore
beach-bird-e-eye-view-daylight-1038374.jpg Birds eye view of water and a dock.	Explore
oceans-eight-trailer-2_h480p.mov Oceans eight movie trailer.	Explore
the-predator-trailer-1_h480p.mov The predator movie trailer.	Explore
Hardwell - Eclipse.mp3 Hardwell Eclipse song.	Explore
dmp_creator.py Source code file for dmplanner.	Explore
dmplanner.py Main source code file for dmplanner.	Explore
gdp_csv.csv GDP world dataset.	Explore
Meteorite-Landings.csv Meteorite landings dataset.	Explore

Fig. 7: Ckan content presentation

For several datatypes an inline preview is possible. This includes for example pictures, text or csv files. For other types of data it is possible to add a picture to the data which will be displayed if the entry is viewed.

Content presentation Fedora:

The content display of a collection in fedora depends on the defined linked data schema. In reality this will most likely result in some kind of children nodes inside a collection node. Fig. 8 shows this approach.

Various Content

[Home](#) / [default_organization](#) / [various-content](#)

Created at

2018-05-15T21:13:59.526Z by bypassAdmin

Last Modified at

2018-05-15T21:14:49.147Z by bypassAdmin

Children 11

- http://localhost:12000/rest/default_organization/various-content/5ba80984-2f40-47df-92ad-f0a45e1c648a
- http://localhost:12000/rest/default_organization/various-content/8eed90ac-5d10-413b-a752-da83365dfb6e
- http://localhost:12000/rest/default_organization/various-content/808623cb-f321-446c-8c39-820b22f5e6d4
- http://localhost:12000/rest/default_organization/various-content/43fbbc4c-1d3c-4b26-903a-06089c17f97f
- http://localhost:12000/rest/default_organization/various-content/06268f35-48e2-44af-8b1b-05eeffc7bbbe
- http://localhost:12000/rest/default_organization/various-content/b91a8bec-8856-455c-a001-23995aa6b45e
- http://localhost:12000/rest/default_organization/various-content/f28d6fdf-6c93-46e0-8934-fb2cf4c6d7ec
- http://localhost:12000/rest/default_organization/various-content/c4ee3320-4adb-43d5-ac6e-676b4d06c63a
- http://localhost:12000/rest/default_organization/various-content/591a1310-9747-405f-83bc-78e3f9e64c05
- http://localhost:12000/rest/default_organization/various-content/e5dcb72c-c125-44f3-b1c5-9f1ebab86361
- http://localhost:12000/rest/default_organization/various-content/431b8147-d258-4ca3-9225-9c94eda04e1e

Fig. 8: Fedora content presentation.

As seen in fig. 8 this solution is not very attractive in a customer facing environment, especially not if auto-generated identifiers are used. But since Fedora is a backend system which does not have a fixed schema for content representation this is hardly a fair comparison to Ckan. Fedora does not provide any kind of preview for the data. The only way to display the files is to download them.

Content search and Discovery Ckan:

Ckan exposes part of the Solr search query syntax for searching. The documentation as well as example search queries did not show any restrictions regarding fields which could be searched.

Similarly, the exposed Solr search query syntax provides a mechanism to perform faceted search.

Ckan provides an optional Datastore extension which creates an ad hoc database for structured data that is uploaded to the repository. With this extension it is not only possible to search inside a resource but also to filter and update the data without having to download and reupload it.

Content search and Discovery Fedora:

In order to search metadata fields in Fedora an external search application (e.g. Solr) as well as Karaf have to be installed and configured. The indexed fields have to be specified in Solr. This makes it possible to search all metadata fields of the repository.

Since the search happens directly through Solr all Solr features can be used which includes the ability to perform a faceted search.

The default Solr schema for Fedora¹² which describes the metadata fields also includes the binary field type which is used for storing files. A comment states that the content should be a Base64 encoded string. Even if this would be ignored and files with easily accessible information (e.g. text) would be stored in the field, the Solr class BinaryField does not allow searching. This means that in contrast to the Ckan functionality it is not easily possible to search the content of stored files. If such a feature is needed one straight-forward solution would be to check if the file which will be stored contains searchable information and to store this information in a separate field in Solr.

User management and access rights Ckan:

The normal user authentication over the web UI uses the username and password. On the profile page of users private API keys are visible. With them it is possible to access API functions which need an authentication. Ckan does not provide any other form of authentication per default. There exist a few 3rd party extensions which for example provide the possibility to log in via google. However, these extensions are not very popular and mostly outdated.

Under normal circumstances Ckan uses organizations as structures to group datasets. Inside an organization Ckan provides three roles which users can acquire: members, editors and admins.

Datasets which are uploaded to Ckan are private per default. Only members of the organization in which the dataset was uploaded can view it. The visibility cannot be changed automatically at a later time. There are a few discussions of adding an embargo period feature in the future although no concrete timeline was given.

The privacy of the data can be managed through the visibility setting and the security ultimately depends on the overall security of the repository provider.

User management and access rights Fedora:

Fedora leaves the authentication and authorization process to the servlet container. Credentials are configured in the container. It is possible to create fedoraAdmin or fedoraUser users. The second category is meant for actual users. A users' access to resources can be managed with WebAC Access Control Lists¹³. With such lists it is possible to define role like access patterns.

¹² <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/fcrepo4-exts/fcrepo4-vagrant-base-box/master/config/schema.xml>

¹³ <https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/FEDORA4x/WebAC+Authorization+Delegate>

Fedora does not seem to have a visibility setting for resources like Ckan has. Therefore, also an embargo period cannot be defined. The security depends on the servlet container in which Fedora runs. The privacy has to be ensured by the creator of the repository since Fedora does not implement such functionality.

Reporting and administration Ckan:

Ckan provides a stats extension which displays several statistics about datasets, revisions, groups and tags. There is also a built-in page view tracking feature as well as an extension which integrates Google Analytics into Ckan for user data.

Fig. 9 shows the central administration panel in the web UI.

Fig.9 Ckan Administration panel.

The installation process of Ckan gave an overview of the areas which have to be configured in order to run the repository. Once this step is done almost all of it can be either configured in a central production configuration file or with a command line tool.

Reporting and administration Fedora:

Fedora does not provide any kind of obvious statistical information. However, there are a few approaches to gather performance metrics¹⁴.

¹⁴ <https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/FEDORA4x/Metrics+Reporting>

Fedora does not provide a central administration panel like Ckan does. Configuration files for fedora can be set at the start of the application. The possible configuration files belong to different tools (e.g. spring, modeshape, etc.) and are normally located in the directory of the tool.

Interoperability Ckan and Fedora:

The Ckan API covers all features that can be performed with the web interface. It is possible to export all metadata key fields including their value. The types are not directly accessible via the API but it would theoretically be possible to export the type definitions through the Postgres instance. Since Fedora only uses strings as fields this step was not necessary. Instead, the textual representation of the fields was imported into Fedora. Due to the fact that Fedora does not have a full-fledged UI, the API exposes the whole functionality.

Theoretically a migration from Ckan to Fedora without data loss would be possible. There are however some Fedora metadata fields which are repository managed and cannot be overwritten. This includes the creation and modification times of the resources. The old timestamps were therefore not migrated. Ultimately it depends on the final use case but these timestamps are probably important in most cases. One possible solution could be to save additional fields with the previous timestamps to the resources. However, this would introduce the special case that new resources do not receive an old timestamp field. A second approach could be to study the Fedora approach of repository managed metadata fields and find a way to change them.

Comparison summary

	Ckan	Fedora
Installation	+ large and active community + good documentation - some documentation steps incomplete - several manual installation steps	+ one-click install - smaller community - problem search infeasible - documentation coupled with other products - quality of documentation lacking
Content Organization	+ all filetypes accepted + automatic custom filetypes possible + versioning with diff	+ all filetypes accepted + snapshot system for versioning
Metadata	+ comprehensive default schema + schema changeable with plugin	+ several repository managed default fields + freedom to define custom schema - default fields not comprehensive
Content presentation	+ appealing list of content + inline preview of data	- only primitive display of node links - no inline view of data
Content search	+ Solr syntax query search + faceted search + possible to search/filter/change content	+ external Solr instance - not possible to search inside content
User management	+ standard username/password authentication + easily accessible private key for API + datasets can be set to private + roles for organization members	+ access to resources can be managed - users have to be configured through the server container
Reporting and administration	+ stats extension for statistics + built in page view tracking feature	+ performance metrics measuring - no built in statistics about users,

	+ possibility to integrate google analytics + central administration panel	resources, etc.
Interoperability	+ exposes entire feature-set over API - no real possibility to export schema definitions	+ exposes entire feature-set over API - some metadata fields not easily overwritable

Recommendation

Based on the comparison above one could say that Ckan is strictly the better repository system but this is only half true. Ckan as seen by the overall positive impression is indeed a very promising repository system. It is user-friendly, has many features and is easily extendable with the plugin system. Fedora on the other hand lacks many features which are almost mandatory for a usable repository system. But Fedora does not try to be a full-fledged repository system; it is a repository backend system. With that in mind Fedora actually does what it advertises.

To sum up, Ckan is a great solution if someone wants to host their own repository system and is happy with the basic structure of Ckan. Fedora on the other hand can be considered as a core part for a new repository system if a linked data storing approach is planned.